

Where have the bumblebees and other wild bees gone? – preliminary results of rapid evaluation in grassland habitats near agricultural fields in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts (Bulgaria)

Ekaterina Kozuharova¹, Toshko Ljubomirov², Dimitar Uzunov³

- (1) [Corresponding author] Medical University of Sofia, Department of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, ina_kozuharova@yahoo.co.uk ✉; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6795-9660>
- (2) Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, toshkoljubomirov@gmail.com ✉; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3202-3309>
- (3) National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, uzunovd@gmail.com ✉; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9742-8956>

Abstract: Ecosystem services from wild bees are related to food production and medicine. However, the global decline of wild bees (including bumblebees) is a well-documented fact. The main factors for this phenomenon are pesticides, habitat loss, changing climate, pathogen transmission etc. The aim of this pilot study is to document the bees' flower visitation activity in several grassland habitats in the close vicinity of agricultural fields in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts. Four study sites were identified with similar plant communities, and transects were carried out in them to observe bee activity. In result we found that wild bees and in particular bumblebees had very low flower visitation activity in the study sites in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts during our short study. We could only speculate about the possible explanation of this fact at the moment. Discussed are the presence of apiaries nearby and intensification of the agriculture in the area during the last decade. This preliminary research demonstrates the necessity of permanent monitoring of wild bees flower visitation activity in the agricultural areas and adjacent territories.

Keywords: bumblebees, ecosystem service, honeybees, pollinator activity, wild bees decline

Introduction

The global bumblebee and other wild bee decline is a well-documented fact and the main factors are pesticides, habitat loss, changing climate, pathogen transmission (Goulson et al., 2008; Cameron & Sadd, 2020; Wood et al., 2020; Parreño et al., 2022; Williams & Hemberger, 2023; Nicholson et al., 2023). The wild bees cannot be replaced for the pollination service by robots (Potts et al., 2018). As a consequence, the plant biodiversity is under threat too (Mayer et al., 2011; Stefanaki et al., 2015; Kozuharova, 2018; Mathiasson & Rehan, 2020; Genung et al., 2023) including medicinal plants (Kozuharova et al., 2020). In other words, many aspects of terrestrial life depend on pollinators. Ecosystem services from wild bees are related to food

production and medicine (Matias et al., 2017; Cole et al., 2020) and legislation and guidelines to control human-created stressors – pesticides as well as pollinator-friendly land management are discussed (Li, 2021). Conservationists promote flower planting to enhance pollinator food reserves. Pollination reservoirs are planted to maintain wild bee populations and hence the crop yield, and profit (Venturini et al., 2017; Ganser et al., 2023; Schmied et al., 2023; Kowalska et al., 2023; Antkowiak et al., 2024). Nesting sites (Antoine & Forrest, 2021; Rahimi et al., 2021) and overwintering sites in the case of *Bombus* (Goulson, 2003) are important too.

While collecting plant material for phytochemical research, we noticed that the usual bee buzz sound was missing in the several grassland habitats in foothills of Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts, Bulgaria. It

Fig. 1. Location of the study sites in Sofia district, Bulgaria.

was a signal that a study was needed, although it was possible to have a very diverse bee fauna with very little buzzing. “Noisy” bees tend to be large bees such as bumblebees and honeybees. Busy bumblebees, belonging to several species, were the usual sight in these grassland habitats some years ago (2013–2015) as we used to visit them regularly although not particularly for pollinators’ research. During these visits we also witnessed that some neighboring grasslands were turned into wheat and sunflower crop fields.

Ten years ago in Pleven District, Bulgaria, roadside verges among certain grasslands and agricultural were a particularly rich habitat for wild bees (Banaszak & Dochkova, 2014). However, lately we recorded poor diversity of wild bees in several lavender fields in Southeastern Dobrudja, a region known for its intensive agriculture (Kozuharova & Vereeken 2024).

The aim of this pilot study is to document the bees’ flower visitation activity with emphasis on the bumblebees in several grassland habitats in close vicinity of agricultural fields.

Material and methods

Study sites and transects

For this study on the flower visitation activity of bees with emphasis on the bumblebees we chose the transect method (Dafni, 1992) namely an adaptation of variable transects walks (Westphal et al., 2008) as

transects are the most efficient method for sampling bumblebees (Hutchinson et al., 2022). The length of each transect was 1000 m and width of 2 m walked for 60 minutes and where the terrain restricted the straight walks to smaller bits of distances at a time the rest of the distance was walked on the same meadow but not on the same route until the 1000 m was accomplished (several dirt roads crossed the study sites 2 and 3 and we followed them). The main study site 1 was a narrow strip of grassland, at both sides of the dirt road, along the northern reservoir bank starting from the dam. One transects along this dirt road were carried out within five times in five different days (in the period 23 June 2023 to 2 July 2023 temperature 25–33°C, clouds 0–6, scale 0–10). The transect of 1000 m walked each day for 60 minutes from 10:10, 16:00, 17:00 and 18:00). For comparison three additional study sites were identified with similar plant communities along dirt roads as follows – two study sites, namely sites 2 and 3 were in the vicinity of study site 1, in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts and one study site, namely site 4 located in Pancharevo Iskar River Gorge (between the mountains [Plana](#) and [Lozenska](#) and at about 20 km South-West from sites 1-3) (Fig. 1) (Table 1).

The visits of all bees observed on the flowers for pollen or nectar collection along the transects per time unit were referred as flower visitation activity and was quantified as activity index (AI_{fv}) (Dafni, 1992), which was calculated for each bee taxon visiting the flowers of each plant taxon as the quotient of the number of individuals recorded and the minutes of

Table 1. Studied sites and its landscape history: June 2011 – July 2022. The coordinates are approximate to mark the study site location.

Site	Locality	Number of transects and length	Number of visits	Date, hours	Landscape history June 2011 – July 2022 and site's habitats (according EUNIS)
Study site 1	Reservoir Ognjanovo 42.617537, 23.751618 Apiary consisted of 21 hives	1; 1000m	5; walked each day for 60 minutes	23 June to 2 July 2023 10:10, 16:00, 17:00 and 18:00	The vegetation consists of pine and deciduous trees, shrubs and hey meadows and pastures. From 2020 the evolution of the vegetation led to afforestation as succession from shrub communities to forest on a small part of the terrain. From 2018 adjacent grassland habitats used for hey were turned into cereal crop fields. The distance from cultivated land is 0.3–0.7 km, with intensification of the agriculture in the cultivated land during the last few years. EUNIS habitat classification – E1 Dry grasslands
Study site 2	Site 2 near Karapoltzi Village 42.615409, 23.703689 Apiary consisted of 45 hives	2; 400 m; 600 m	1; walked both for 60 minutes	10:10 – 11:10 on 24 June 2023,	It is a field characterised by hygrophytic tree vegetation, shrubs and pastures. The place did not go through a significant evolution during the last 10 years. The distance from cultivated land is 0.3 km, with intensification of the agriculture in the cultivated land during the last few years. EUNIS – E2 Mesic grasslands
Study site 3	Site 3 near Gorna Rakovitza Village 42.607041, 23.832222	2; 500 m; 500 m	1; walked both for 60 minutes	18:40 – 19:40 on 2 July 2023	The vegetation consists mainly of meadows and single deciduous trees. The place did not go through a significant change during the last 10 years. The distance from the nearest cultivated land is 1.5–1.7 km with intensification of the agriculture in the cultivated land during the last few years, with change of the land use nearby from pasture to arable (grain) fields. EUNIS habitat classification – E1 Dry grasslands
Study site 4	Site 4 near Pasarel Village 42.534450, 23.523027	1; 1000 m	1; walked both for 60 minutes	16:50 – 17:50 on 3 July 2023	It is a field with hygrophytic tree vegetation, meadows with single trees in them. The study site did not undergo significant change during the last 10 years. From 2015 adjacent grassland habitats used for hey were turned into cereal cropfields. The distance from the nearest cultivated land is 0.1 km but the size of cultivated land is not big and intensification of the agriculture is not obvious (no land rennes registered in the area). EUNIS habitat classification – E1 Dry grasslands

observation for multiplied by 60 minutes (Figs 3, 6 and 7).

The observation hours were chosen predominantly late in the afternoon, because of the hot weather. Solitary wild bees tend to be active before the main heat of the day (Willmer & Stone, 2004) but we aimed mainly the large and noisy bees. Bumblebees are known to be less tolerant to high temperature compared to honeybees (Corbet et al., 1993; Karbassioon et al., 2023). At the same time, it is known that bumblebees such as *Bombus terrestris* and *B. pascuorum* are active within the period 08:00 to 23:00 and the circadian clock of the foragers depends on light intensity and temperature (Spaethe & Weidenmüller, 2002; Stelzer & Chittka, 2010; Karbassioon & Stanley, 2023). These boreal insects have been documented active till sunset even at higher altitude in our previous studies in Bulgarian

mountains (Kozuharova & Firmage, 2007; Kozuharova & Firmage, 2009; Kozuharova & Simeonov, 2022; Valchev & Kozuharova, 2022).

Observations and sampling

In order to trace the history of the landscape (Table 1) Google Earth Pro was used following standard methods (Gigante et al. 2016). The entomophilous plant species were listed with regard to their flowering abundance at each day of observations following a modification of the Braun-Blanquet scale (Braun-Blanquet, 1964) as follows: 3 – range of cover 25–50%, 2 – range of cover 5–25%, 1 – range of cover <5% with numerous individuals, r – range of cover <5% with few individuals, + – range of cover <5% with sporadic individuals. We listed only the

Fig. 2. Plant communities in the study sites: Legend: A to C – study site 1 (42.617537, 23.751618); D – study site 2 (42.615409, 23.703689); E – study site 3 (42.607041, 23.832222); F – study site 4 (42.534450, 23.523027). Note: the coordinates are approximate to mark the study site location

entomophilous plants in flower and considered the average range of cover of the flowering individuals along the whole transect. We looked carefully for the bees visiting the flowering plants and recorded them for each plant species along the transect. Identification of the bees was performed in the field at most detailed possible taxonomic level (family, genus or species) as well as by photographs of the observed bees that were taken along the transect. Olympus E 500 and Zuiko Digital 14-45 mm f3.5–5.6 was used.

Results

Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts

Study site 1

Floral food resources were lavish at study site 1 with 47 plant taxa recorded along the transect. (Table 2, Fig. 2). The abundance of some species increased (*Sideritis montana* L., *Teucrium chamaedrys* L., *Salvia nemorosa* L., Table 2) or decreased (*Astra-*

galus onobrychis L., Table 2) during the period of observation (23 June 2023 to 2 July 2023), reflecting the flowering phenology in the plant community of the study site 1.

Honeybees, *Apis mellifera* Linnaeus, 1758 (Apidae) workers were recorded with highest flower visitation activity (Fig. 3). At the average 91 honeybee individuals per day or ($AI_{fv}=90,6$) were recorded on the transect during the period of observation and the workers favoured *Dorycnium herbaceum* Vill. ($AI_{fv}=47.2$) *Salvia nemorosa* L. ($AI_{fv}=12.2$), *Teucrium chamaedrys* ($AI_{fv}=8.4$), *Salvia aethiopsis* L. ($AI_{fv}=6.2$), *Astragalus onobrychis* L. ($AI_{fv}=6.1$), *Onobrychis arenaria* (Kit.) DC. ($AI_{fv}=3.9$), *Sideritis montana* L. ($AI_{fv}=2.3$) and few more on several other plants (Fig. 3). The flower visitation activity of honeybees reflected in general the abundance of flowering food plants (Table 2), and the presence of an apiary consisted of 21 bee hives in the middle of the transect (Fig. 3). As an exception can be pointed the relative low abundance of *S. aethiopsis* (Table 2) and the high visitation activity of honeybees in its flowers. This can be explained with the location of the

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Table 2. Abundance of flowering plant species at the study sites – listed are only the blooming entomophilous plants and the cover of the flowering individuals follows a modification of the Braun-Blanquet scale (Braun-Blanquet, 1964). The plants are listed in the table according to their abundance. Note: the coordinates are approximate to mark the study site location.

Study sites in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts				Study site in Pancharevo Gorge			
Site 1 near Reservoir Ognjanovo 42.617537, 23.751618 Apiary consisted of 21 hives		Site 2 near Karapoltzi Village 42.615409, 23.703689 Apiary consisted of 45 hives		Site 3 near Gorna Rakovitza Village 42.607041, 23.832222		Site 4 near Pasarel Village 42.534450, 23.523027	
Plant species	Br-BI	Plant species	Br-BI	Plant species	Br-BI	Plant species	Br-BI
<i>Astragalus onobrychis</i> L.	3-R	<i>Thymus</i> sp. div.	4	<i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i> L.	3	<i>Orlaya grandiflora</i> (L.) Hoffm.	2
<i>Sideritis montana</i> L.	R-3	<i>Chamomilla recutita</i> (L.) Rauschert	R	<i>Orlaya grandiflora</i> (L.) Hoffm.	3	<i>Vicia tenuifolia</i> Roth	2
<i>Medicago falcata</i> L.	3	<i>Dianthus campestris</i> M. Bieb.	R	<i>Medicago falcata</i> L.	3	<i>Salvia verticillata</i> L.	2
<i>Dorycnium herbaceum</i> Vill.	3	<i>Potentilla argentea</i> L.	R	<i>Coronilla varia</i> L.	3	<i>Vicia grandiflora</i> Scop.	1
<i>Coronilla varia</i> L.	3	<i>Trifolium rubens</i> L.	R	<i>Thymus</i> sp.	2	<i>Trifolium campestre</i> Schreb.	1
<i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i> L.	R-2	<i>Moenchia mantica</i> (L.) Bartl.	+	<i>Sideritis montana</i> L.	2	<i>Galium molugo</i> group	1
<i>Salvia nemorosa</i> L.	R-2	<i>Echium vulgare</i> L.	+	<i>Trifolium campestre</i> Schreb.	1	<i>Rubus</i> sp.	1
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i> L.	2			<i>Rhinanthus rumelicus</i> Velen.	1	<i>Stachys germanica</i> L.	R
<i>Convolvulus cantabrica</i> L.	2			<i>Achillea millefolium</i> group	1	<i>Lotus corniculatus</i> L.	R
<i>Achillea clypeolata</i> Sm.	2			<i>Xeranthemum annuum</i> L.	R	<i>Medicago falcata</i> L.	R
<i>Onobrychis arenaria</i> (Kit.) DC.	1			<i>Trifolium alpestre</i> L.	R	<i>Thymus</i> sp.	R
<i>Galium molugo</i> group	1			<i>Salvia verticillata</i> L.	R	<i>Trifolium repens</i> L.	R
<i>Digitalis lanata</i> Ehrh.	1			<i>Salvia nemorosa</i> L.	R	<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i> L.	+
<i>Astragalus cicer</i> L.	1			<i>Potentilla recta</i> L. group	R	<i>Asperula cynanchica</i> L.	+
<i>Acinos suaveolens</i> (Sibth. & Sm.) G. Don	1			<i>Lotus corniculatus</i> L.	R	<i>Echium vulgare</i> L.	+
<i>Trifolium campestre</i> Schreb.	R			<i>Digitalis lanata</i> Ehrh.	R	<i>Anchusa officinalis</i> L.	+
<i>Thymus</i> sp. div.	R			<i>Astragalus cicer</i> L.	R	<i>Centaurea phrygia</i> L.	+
<i>Stachys recta</i> L.	R			<i>Anthyllis vulneraria</i> L.	R	<i>Digitalis lanata</i> Ehrh.	+
<i>Stachys germanica</i> L.	R			<i>Petrorhagia prolifera</i> (L.) P. W. Ball & Heywood	+	<i>Dianthus campestris</i> M. Bieb.	+
<i>Salvia verticillata</i> L.	R			<i>Hypericum perforatum</i> L.	+	<i>Knautia arvensis</i> (L.) Coult.	+
<i>Muscari comosum</i> (L.) Mill.	R			<i>Potentilla argentea</i> L.	+	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i> L.	+
<i>Linum austriacum</i> L.	R			<i>Onobrychis arenaria</i> (Kit.) DC.	+	<i>Potentilla argentea</i> L.	+
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i> L.	R			<i>Knautia arvensis</i> (L.) Coult.	+	<i>Galium verum</i> L.	+

Table 1 continued...

<i>Galium verum</i> L.	R			<i>Helianthemum nummulariifolium</i> Spruner ex Willk.	+	<i>Petrorhagia prolifera</i> (L.) P. W. Ball & Heywood	+
<i>Eryngium campestre</i> L.	R			<i>Genista tinctoria</i> L.	+	<i>Achillea millefolium</i> group	+
<i>Echium vulgare</i> L.	R			<i>Galium verum</i> L.	+	<i>Dorycnium herbaceum</i> Vill.	+
<i>Achillea millefolium</i> L. group	R			<i>Echium vulgare</i> L.	+		
<i>Verbena officinalis</i> L.	+			<i>Dianthus cruentus</i> Griseb.	+		
<i>Trifolium pratense</i> L.	+			<i>Crupina crupinastrum</i> (Moris) Vis.	+		
<i>Trifolium pannonicum</i> Jacq.	+			<i>Centaurea stoebe</i> L.	+		
<i>Tragopogon dubius</i> Scop.	+			<i>Astragalus onobrychis</i> L.	+		
<i>Salvia aethiopsis</i> L.	+			<i>Achillea clypeolata</i> Sm.	+		
<i>Rhinanthus rumelicus</i> Velen.	+						
<i>Potentilla recta</i> L. group	+						
<i>Potentilla argentea</i> L.	+						
<i>Petrorhagia prolifera</i> (L.) P. W. Ball & Heywood	+						
<i>Melilotus officinalis</i> (L.) Lam.	+						
<i>Melilotus albus</i> Medik.	+						
<i>Jurinea mollis</i> (L.) Rchb.	+						
<i>Hypericum rumeliacum</i> Boiss.	+						
<i>Filipendula vulgaris</i> Moench	+						
<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> L.	+						
<i>Clinopodium vulgare</i> L.	+						
<i>Chamaecytisus albus</i> (Hacq.) Rothm	+						
<i>Anthemis tinctoria</i> L.	+						
<i>Ajuga chamaepitys</i> subsp. <i>chia</i> (Schreb.) Arcang.	+						
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i> L.	+						

few *S. aethiopsis* individuals in near vicinity to the apiary. But the multifloral big inflorescence of this plant is obviously attractive to bees because beside honeybees there were recorded also carpenter bee, buff-tailed bumblebee, and *Megchile* sp. (Fig. 3).

The number of observed bee taxa apart from the honeybees was between 0 and 7 on each visit of the transect or at the average 3 taxa daily during the period of observations of 5 days – see Table 3. Additionally, these were sporadic visits of wild bees

Table 3. List of bee taxa at the study sites.

Family and species	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4
APIDAE				
<i>Apis mellifera</i> Linnaeus, 1758	+	+	+	+
<i>Bombus</i> cf. <i>terrestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+	+
<i>Bombus</i> cf. <i>lapidarius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)				+
<i>Bombus</i> cf. <i>hortorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)				+
<i>Bombus</i> cf. <i>pascuorum</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	+			+
<i>Bombus haematurus</i> Kriechbaumer, 1870				+
<i>Ceratina</i> sp.	+			
<i>Xylocopa</i> sp.	+			
<i>Xylocopa iris</i> (Christ, 1791)				+
<i>Amegilla</i> sp.				+
<i>Eucera</i> sp.				+
ANDRENIDAE				
<i>Andrena</i> sp.	+			+
MEGACHILIDAE				
<i>Megachile</i> sp.	+			+
<i>Osmia</i> cf. <i>andrenoides</i> Spinola, 1808	+			
HALICTIDAE				
<i>Halictus</i> sp.	+			
COLLETIDAE				
<i>Colletes</i> sp.	+			

and the average flower visitation activity of each taxon for the whole observation period was very low – between 0.2 and 1.0 on each of the food plants or between 0.2 to 1.8 along the transect on all the food plants together favoured by a particular bee taxon (Fig. 3). *Andrena* (*Zonandrena*) *flavipes* Panzer, 1799 (Andrenidae) females were the most common of the wild bees at site 1 at the average ($AI_{fv}=1.8$) with most preferred *D. herbaceum* ($AI_{fv}=0.8$) and *Digitalis lanata* Ehrh. ($AI_{fv}=0.4$), followed by *Bombus* cf. *terrestris* at the average ($AI_{fv}=1.1$) with most preferred *S. aethiopsis* ($AI_{fv}=0.5$) and *S. nemorosa* ($AI_{fv}=0.4$) (Figs 3–5).

Study site 2

Floral food resources were plentiful at study site 2 with a high abundance of *Thymus* sp. div., however few other plant taxa were recorded along this transect.

(Table 2, Fig. 2). Honeybees flower visitation activity was highest at this study site (145 workers were recorded during the transect) and all of them favoured the patches of *Thymus* sp. div. with ($AI_{fv}=145$). It must be noted that 50 m away from the transect in study site 2 were located 45 bee hives. No wild bees were recorded here except one dead worker of *B. cf. terrestris* (Fig. 4).

Study site 3

Floral food resources were rich at study site 3 with a high abundance of flowering taxa (Table 2, Fig. 2) The recorded low flower visitation activity at study site 3 (Fig. 6) was surprising considering the abundance of flowering food resources (Table 2).

Only few honeybees ($AI_{fv}=9$) and a worker of *B. cf. terrestris* ($AI_{fv}=1$) were recorded along the transect at study site 3.

Fig. 3. Study site 1 – average flower visitation activity (AI_v) of bees on each of the flowering food plant taxa during the period 24 June 2023 – 2 July 2023, Legend: X – axis bee taxa, Y axis – plant taxa, Z axis (vertical) – values of the Braun-Blanquet scale for each plant taxa and number of individuals per hour visiting the same plant taxa).

Fig. 4. Total average activity (number of individuals per hour) of wild bees versus honeybees at each study sites.

Fig. 5. Wild bees: A – *Andrena* (*Zonandrena*) *flavipes* Panzer, 1799 (Andrenidae) on *Dorycnium herbaceum* at study site 1; B – *Eucera* sp. (Apidae) on *Vicia tenuifolia* at study site 4; C – *Bombus haematurus* Kriechbaumer, 1870 on *Vicia tenuifolia* at study site 4; D – *Bombus pascuorum* (Scopoli, 1763) on *Stachys germanica* L. at study site 4.

Study site 4

Floral food resources were plentiful at study site 4 regarding the high abundance of flowering taxa (Table 2), but in comparison to sites 1 and 3 species richness of entomophilous plants was lower.

Totally 36 honeybees were recorded on the transect during the period of observation and the workers favoured *Salvia verticillata* L. ($AI_{iv}=14$) and *Vicia tenuifolia* Roth ($AI_{iv}=12$), followed by *Echium vulgare* L. ($AI_{iv}=4$) and few others (Fig. 7). Apart from honeybee workers, at this site 10 taxa of wild bees were recorded (Figs 4 and 7). The flower

visitation activity of honeybees ($AI_{iv}=36$) was lower compared to the total flower visitation activity of all wild bees ($AI_{iv}=47$) recorded along the transect at this study site (Figs 4). The flower visitation activity of bumblebees belonging to at least 5 taxa was ($AI_{iv}=23$) as follows *Bombus pascuorum* (Scopoli, 1763) at *Stachys germanica* L. ($AI_{iv}=7$), *B. haematurus* Kriechbaumer, 1870 at *Vicia tenuifolia* ($AI_{iv}=4$), *Bombus* cf. *terrestris* at *V. tenuifolia* ($AI_{iv}=3$), at *Vicia grandiflora* Scop. ($AI_{iv}=2$), at *Rubus* sp. ($AI_{iv}=2$) etc. (Figs 4, 5 and 7). *V. grandiflora* was attractive to other wild bees such as *Amegilla* sp. ($AI_{iv}=7$), *Eucera* sp. ($AI_{iv}=6$) and *Megachile* sp. ($AI_{iv}=4$) (Figs 4, 5 and 7).

Fig. 6. Study site 3 – average flower visitation activity (AI_v) of bees on each the flowering food plant taxa on 2 July 2023, Legend: X – axis bee taxa, Y axis – plant taxa, Z axis (vertical) – values of the Braun-Blanquet scale for each plant taxa and number of individuals per hour visiting the same plant taxa).

Also, at this study site 4 in Pancharevo Gorge wild bees were notably more active compared to the study sites 1 to 3 in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts (Fig. 4).

Discussion

The overall count of wild bee taxa reached nine species at study site 1 (Fig. 3). It was recorded as a result of cumulative observations during five days with five visits of the transect along the same rout of 1 km (dirt road beside the reservoir). Daily the maximum count did not exceed 7 taxa. At study site 4 were counted ten taxa of wild bees (Fig. 7). This

number of bee taxa was recorded during just one visit on a transect along 1 km of dirt road at study site 4, a day after the last transect at study site 1 was accomplished. It is hard to find an explanation to the observed low wild bee flower visitation activity in all study sites in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts. The wild bees had very low flower visitation activity in all study sites in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts (Fig. 4), while the honeybees there were more or less active flower visitors and foragers at the study sites 1 and 2 (Fig. 4). This result could be affected by the presence of apiaries near study sites 1 and 2. The honeybees compete with bumblebees, reducing their number, and the body size of the workers (Forup & Memmott,

Fig. 7. Study site 4 – average flower visitation (AI_n) activity of bees on each the flowering food plant taxa on 3 July 2023, Legend: X – axis bee taxa, Y axis – plant taxa, Z axis (vertical) – values of the Braun-Blanquet scale for each plant taxa and number of individuals per hour visiting the same plant taxa).

2005; Goulson & Sparrow, 2009; Henry & Rodet, 2018; Wignall et al., 2020; Iwasaki & Hogendoorn, 2022; Maurer et al., 2024). A niche overlap is documented for the genera *Andrena*, *Halictus* s.l., *Nomada* and the honeybee in various grassland habitats in Pleven District, Bulgaria (Banaszak et al., 2015). Additionally, honeybees are known to transmit pathogens to the wild bees (Tehel et al., 2016; Iwasaki & Hogendoorn, 2022).

It is worth discussing the very low species richness of flowering plants at study site 2 (Table 2), due to ruderalisation in the last 15 years (Table 1). Many wild bees forage not far away from their nests and they are not present in the area where their food requirements are not satisfied (Gathmann & Tschardt, 2002; Zurbuchen et al., 2010). Therefore, if the various species of *Thymus* are not suitable for them, they would be absent. Bumblebees are polylectic as well as many other wild bees (Venn et al., 2023). Polylectic bees, also known as generalists, collect nectar and/or

pollen from a wide range of unrelated plants. Bumblebees can also fly long distances (Osborne et al., 2012; Rao & Strange, 2012). That is why the lack of bumblebees and other polylectic wild bees at study site 2 cannot be easily explained. Change in land cover is thought to be one of the key drivers of pollinator declines (Senapathi et al., 2015). The recorded low bumblebees' abundance/diversity may be a result of the landscape change in the areas surrounding the study sites in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts. Hundreds of hectares of fields of corn, sunflower and barley nearby the study sites (Fig. 1, Table 1) are an object of the recent extensive agricultural use.

The transect at study site 3 where the food resources were lavish (Table 2, Fig. 6) should be interpreted with caution. Although it took place the same day and only half an hour after the transect at study site 1 was accomplished, it was late enough in the evening. This might have influenced the activity of the small bees.

The use of insecticides and other pesticides in the agricultural area of Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts should not be excluded as possible explanation of the observed low activity of bees in the study sites. The intensive agriculture is known to negatively impact wild bees (Le Feon et al., 2010; Wenzel et al., 2020). Agrochemicals act synergistically in non-target decrease of bees (Siviter et al., 2021; Botías et al., 2021). Particularly the non-target negative effect of the pesticide on bumblebees is well demonstrated (Nicholson et al., 2023) and moreover honeybees are less affected (Rundlöf et al., 2015). At the moment data about pesticide use in the region is missing and such explanation seems so speculative, especially for the site 3.

Conclusion

Wild bees and in particular bumblebees had very low flower visitation activity in the study sites in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts during our short study. We could only speculate about the possible explanation of this fact at the moment. This preliminary research demonstrates the necessity of permanent monitoring of wild bees flower visitation activity in the agricultural areas and adjacent territories.

Authors' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Ekaterina Kozuharova: conceptualisation, investigation, methodology, supervision, visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Toshko Ljubomirov: investigation, writing—review and editing; Dimitar Uzunov: methodology, writing—review and editing.

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